

Blind Image Decomposition for Recovering Overlapping Text Layers on Palimpsests

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Abstract. Recovering the scriptio inferior (undertext) from palimpsests remains a significant challenge in digital heritage and historical document analysis due to the severe degradation of the scraped ink and complex interference from the visible scriptio superior (overtext). A prime example is the collection at the Biblioteca Capitolare of Verona; despite previous digitization efforts, the undertext in these manuscripts often remains illegible to Optical Character Recognition (OCR) models and, in severe cases, even to expert paleographers. Traditional enhancement techniques frequently fail to disentangle these overlapping signals effectively. This paper presents a novel approach to this problem using Blind Image Decomposition (BID). We modify the standard BID architecture to incorporate asymmetric decoders, allowing for specialized processing of the distinct text layers. To address the erosion of the undertext, we introduce a feature consistency loss to ensure robust latent representations, alongside a connectivity-preserving loss designed to enforce structural continuity in faint, fragmented strokes. Furthermore, to bridge the domain gap between training and inference, we employ a masked pre-training strategy on synthetic mixtures that leverages the spatial priors of the undertext script. Experimental results show superior separation performance compared to the baseline BID method. Finally, qualitative evaluation on the degraded Codex Veronensis XL from the Biblioteca Capitolare confirms the model’s efficacy as a tool for paleographic analysis. Code and data will be released upon acceptance.

Keywords: Blind image decomposition · Palimpsest · Overlapping text separation.

1 Introduction

1.1 Palimpsests at the Capitolare

Derived from the Greek *palin* (“again”) and *psao* (“scrape”), a palimpsest is a manuscript born from scarcity [1]: a parchment whose original text (scriptio inferior) was erased to allow for the inscription of a new layer (scriptio superior). These stratified documents act as accidental time capsules, often preserving historically significant texts that were considered obsolete by medieval scribes.

However, recovering these lost layers is not straightforward. The undertext is not just hidden, it is also physically degraded by the scraping attempts of the original scribe, and in some cases, chemically corrupted by modern "restoration" attempts [2].

To investigate this challenge, we focus on the collection of the *Biblioteca Capitolare of Verona*. Documented as active as early as 517 AD [3], the Capitolare is the oldest continuously operating library in the Western world. It stands as a testament to resilience, having survived the plague of 1630 (which decimated the Chapter and erased the memory of its "hidden" codices), the Napoleonic seizures of 1797, and the Allied bombings of 1945 [3]. Among its survivors is the *Codex Veronensis XL* (Fig. 1), a manuscript that embodies the extreme limits of digital readability.

The Codex XL is a chaotic mixture of eras. The visible oertext preserves St. Gregory the Great’s *Moralia in Job*, written in a dense 7th- or 8th-century Luxeuil minuscule. Beneath this lies a far older treasure: a 5th-century witness to Virgil’s *Bucolica*, *Georgica*, and *Aeneis*, written in Rustic Capitalis. The fragment holds exceptional philological value as one of the seven surviving codices Vergiliani antiquiores, i.e., early witnesses to the Virgilian corpus dating from the 4th to the 6th centuries.

Fig. 1. A folio from Codex Veronensis XL photographed under visible light. A portion of the palimpsest is shown at higher magnification to improve the visibility of the overlapping texts. The dense oertext is written in Luxeuil minuscule, while the degraded undertext is in Rustic Capitalis. The image is oriented according to the oertext, with the undertext appearing inverted.

The difficulty of recovering the Veronensis XL is compounded by what is described as an “archaeology of destruction” [4]. Upon the rediscovery of the undertext in 1817 [5], 19th-century philologists resorted to aggressive chemical treatments to make the faded ink visible. Angelo Mai (an important figure in palimpsest studies), recognizing the value of the scholia, treated the margins with oak-gall tincture, an alcohol-based reagent that temporarily enhanced the metallic ink but permanently stained the parchment and corroded the text over time. Later interventions introduced even more damaging substances, such as

Giobert's tincture, creating a complex chemical stratification that defies linear separation [2].

With the parchment continuing to deteriorate, digitization is a matter of urgent preservation.

1.2 The Challenge in Recovering the Text

The conventional approach to recovering hidden undertext relies on non-invasive imaging techniques, such as Multispectral Imaging (MSI), often coupled with statistical decomposition methods like Principal Component Analysis (PCA) or Independent Component Analysis (ICA) [9]. These methods operate on the premise that the scriptio superior and scriptio inferior possess distinct spectral signatures that can be decorrelated. While successful in cases of distinct ink compositions, these techniques often fail when addressing the complex, non-linear degradations found in palimpsests like the Codex Veronensis XL. As demonstrated in the preliminary analysis of Codex XL using a Phase One Rainbow MSI system [13], the undertext could not be effectively isolated in specific Infrared (IR) or Ultraviolet (UV) bandwidths (Fig. 2). This is largely due to the severe degradation of the parchment. Consequently, the undertext remains entangled with the overtext in the visible spectrum.

Fig. 2. A portion of Codex XL photographed under Ultraviolet (UV), Visible (VIS), and Infrared (IR) illumination. The UV image reveals traces of chemical reagents previously applied to enhance the visibility of the undertext.

A parallel body of research addresses the problem of overlapping text as bleed-through removal [10]. These computational models typically employ physically inspired constraints to identify and suppress text seeping through from

the verso side of a page. However, their primary objective is the preservation of the foreground (overtext), often treating the background signal as noise to be discarded. This formulation is ill-suited for palimpsest research, where the undertext is the signal of interest. Furthermore, these rigid physical models struggle to capture the high variability of degradation on palimpsests.

Deep generative models have attempted to disentangle text layers by learning data-driven priors. Starynska et al. [11] proposed a framework that treats separation as an inverse problem, using a GAN pre-trained on an external clean manuscript to guide an iterative reconstruction of the undertext. While pioneering, this analysis-by-synthesis approach suffers from high computational latency, as it requires hundreds of optimization iterations for every image patch. Furthermore, it relies heavily on the availability of a perfectly matching external proxy for training, which is rare for unique ancient codices. It also often struggles to capture the structural continuity of continuous scripts. Other attempts to frame separation as an inpainting task have emerged [12], though they typically lack rigorous quantitative evaluation on real historical degradation.

1.3 Contributions

To address the limitations of current imaging and computational techniques in revealing palimpsest undertext, a novel Blind Image Decomposition (BID) framework [14] is proposed, tailored specifically to the challenges of recovering undertext from palimpsests. The main contributions of this work are as follows:

1. **Asymmetric BID Architecture:** Standard symmetric decoders are replaced with an asymmetric generator tailored to the morphological imbalance of palimpsests. The undertext head is equipped with CBAM and Dilated Residual Blocks, for reconstruction of faint, fragmented undertext strokes.

2. **Two-Stage training:** A tailored training pipeline is introduced. Masked pretraining is first applied to the undertext decoder to learn the structural priors of the target script, which is subsequently followed by end-to-end network fine-tuning.

3. **Specialized Loss Functions:** A feature consistency loss is implemented to ensure the distinct latent features of the undertext are captured by the network. Additionally, a connectivity loss is applied during fine-tuning to bridge gaps in eroded ink and ensure continuous character strokes.

4. **Historical Validation:** The practical efficacy of the model is demonstrated on degraded patches from the Codex Veronensis XL (Biblioteca Capitolare), establishing its viability as a non-invasive computational tool for paleographical analysis.

2 Blind Image Decomposition

Blind Image Decomposition (BID) is a computer vision task of decomposing a single superimposed image into its constituent underlying components in a blind setting, meaning both the source components and the mixing mechanism

are unknown. Unlike conventional decomposition tasks that assume a fixed linear combination or a known number of layers, BID treats the observed image I as an arbitrary function of latent sources:

$$I = f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \quad (1)$$

where f is an unknown mixing function and $\{x_i\}$ are the source components. Recent work, such as the Blind Image Decomposition Network (BIDeN) [14], utilizes Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) to solve this by learning to predict both the source components involved and their separated forms from a single input.

Overlapping text in historical documents, such as palimpsests, reused bindings, show-through, or offset ink, naturally fits the BID formulation for several reasons. First, the interaction between ink, substrate, aging processes, and imaging conditions results in complex, often non-linear mixing effects that are difficult to model explicitly. BID addresses this by learning the separation implicitly, without prescribing a specific mixing function. Second, overlapping text layers typically contribute unequally to the observed image, with secondary or erased writing often exhibiting very low contrast. BID is explicitly designed to handle such imbalanced mixtures, where some components contribute only weak visual signals. Finally, ground-truth separated layers are rarely available for historical material. The BID framework reduces reliance on pixel-wise paired supervision by combining adversarial, perceptual, and reconstruction-based objectives, making it suitable for palimpsest analysis with limited or indirect supervision.

Therefore, the overlapping historical text can be seen as a special case of blind image decomposition, where each textual stratum constitutes a latent source component and the writing surface acts as an unknown mixing medium. Within this perspective, BID provides a principled and flexible framework for separating superimposed text without imposing unrealistic assumptions on degradation physics.

3 Proposed Method

We approach the recovery of palimpsests text layers as a decomposition task trained on synthetic data. Our goal is to train a deep network that takes a single observed RGB image $I \in R^{H \times W \times 3}$ and predicts the two distinct layers: the scriptio superior (overtext) S_{over} and the scriptio inferior (undertext) S_{under} . The proposed BID framework is constrained to a two-component decomposition ($N = 2$). In this formulation, the background of the image mixture is not treated as a separate, recoverable source. Instead, it is formulated as unstructured noise that must be actively discarded by the network.

3.1 Network Architecture: Asymmetric BID with Attention

We modify the baseline Blind Image Decomposition (BID) architecture to address the morphological disparity between the text layers. Our model features a Shared Encoder followed by two specialized Asymmetric Decoders.

Fig. 3. The architecture of the proposed model.

Multi-scale Encoder (E) A deep convolutional encoder processes the input image I , extracting a shared high-dimensional feature representation $Z = E(I)$. Similar to the BIDE N [14], the encoder (E) employs a multi-branch architecture. The resulting multi-scale feature maps are subsequently concatenated along the channel dimension to form a single, fused latent representation.

Asymmetric Decoders To disentangle the layers, we employ two decoders:

Overtext Head (H_{over}) A standard convolutional decoder designed to reconstruct the dominant S_{over} .

Undertext Head (H_{under}) Because the undertext is typically faint and structurally broken, H_2 employs a specialized architecture. It first processes the latent features through a Convolutional Block Attention Module (CBAM) [8] to apply channel and spatial attention, highlighting faint text signals. This is followed by a Context Aggregation stream containing four Residual Block with Dilation [6] modules with exponentially increasing dilation rates ($d = 1, 2, 4, 8$). This drastically expands the receptive field without resolution loss, allowing the network to connect fragmented text strokes before standard upsampling.

Discriminator (D) The discriminator is similar to BIDE N . It features a shared feature-extraction trunk that splits into two functional branches. The separation branch (D_S) classifies inputs as real or generated. Concurrently, the prediction branch (D_P) operates as a multi-label classifier, identifying the exact source components present within the mixed input image I .

The proposed architecture is presented in Fig. 3.

3.2 Loss Functions

Training is done using synthetic mixtures where the ground truth components ($S_{over}^{gt}, S_{under}^{gt}$) are known. A compound objective function is applied directly to the predicted outputs. The original BDeN framework relies on an adversarial loss (\mathcal{L}_{GAN}) [15], a perceptual VGG loss (\mathcal{L}_{VGG}) [16], and a global pixel-wise L_1 reconstruction loss (\mathcal{L}_{rec}). To ensure a better reconstruction of the degraded undertext scripture, the following two specialized loss functions are also included.

Feature Consistency Loss (\mathcal{L}_{feat}) To encourage the multi-scale encoder (E) to actively filter out noise, erosion artifacts, and oertext interference in the latent space, a feature consistency regularization term is applied. It explicitly penalizes the L_1 distance between the encoded latent representation of the clean target undertext (S_{under}^{gt}) and the encoded representation of the noisy, mixed palimpsest (z_{mixed}):

$$\mathcal{L}_{feat} = \|E(S_{under}^{gt}) - E(z_{mixed})\|_1 \quad (2)$$

Feature consistency has been previously implemented successfully in the context of text image reconstruction [18].

Connectivity-Preserving Loss (\mathcal{L}_{conn}) To enforce the structural and topological integrity of the reconstructed handwriting, we incorporate a Connectivity-preserving Loss (\mathcal{L}_{conn}) [19, 20]. Unlike standard pixel-wise metrics, this objective explicitly targets morphological artifacts by performing connected component analysis on the predicted text masks. The final loss is computed as a weighted interpolation between the base pixel-wise error (\mathcal{L}_0) and the topologically penalized error, ensuring the generated undertext maintains legible, continuous character trajectories:

$$\mathcal{L}_{conn} = (1 - \alpha) \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{L}_0] + \alpha \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{L}_0 \odot W_{topology}] \quad (3)$$

Where α dictates the strength of the topological focus, and $W_{topology}$ is the dynamically generated weight map containing the heavy penalties for bridge and gap pixels.

The complete, compound objective function for the generator is formulated as a weighted sum of the individual loss components:

$$\mathcal{L}_G = \lambda_{GAN} \mathcal{L}_{GAN} + \lambda_{rec} \mathcal{L}_{rec} + \lambda_{VGG} \mathcal{L}_{VGG} + \lambda_{feat} \mathcal{L}_{feat} + \lambda_{conn} \mathcal{L}_{conn} \quad (4)$$

During training, \mathcal{L}_{GAN} , \mathcal{L}_{VGG} , \mathcal{L}_{rec} , \mathcal{L}_{feat} are set to 1, 10, 30, and 10 respectively. \mathcal{L}_{conn} is set to 0 during pre-training and set to 1 during the fine-tuning phase.

3.3 Masked Pretraining Strategy

To address the ill-posed nature of separating severely fragmented text, we introduce a masked pretraining stage that initializes the undertext decoder (D_{under}) with a robust structural prior (Fig. 5). We formulate this as a self-supervised task, where the network learns to approximate the manifold of undertext writing style by reconstructing occluded inputs. Previous work in document analysis has demonstrated that self-supervised masked pretraining is highly effective for learning representations of text images [17].

The mask is a binary mask $M \in \{0, 1\}^{H \times W}$ sampled from a Bernoulli distribution with parameter $p = 0.5$, spatially structured as random rectangular blocks (Fig. 4). The corrupted input \tilde{S} is obtained via the Hadamard product:

$$\tilde{S} = S_{under} \odot M \quad (5)$$

D_{under} is optimized to predict the original uncorrupted signal S_{under} from the partial view \tilde{S} . The objective function calculates loss only on the masked regions, forcing the model to infer missing topology from global context rather than copying visible pixels:

$$\mathcal{L}_{MIM} = \|(S_{under} - D_{under}(\tilde{S})) \odot (\mathbf{1} - M)\|_1 \quad (6)$$

Fig. 4. Examples of masked samples and their ground truth.

4 Experimental Setup and Training Details

4.1 Synthetic Data Generation

To overcome the lack of paired ground-truth data, the network is trained on synthetic palimpsest mixtures generated on-the-fly. The textual content is rendered using a curated selection of medieval Latin fonts. For instance, Luxeuil minuscule [28] is utilized to generate solid, high-contrast overtext, while Rustic Capital [21] is employed for the undertext. To physically replicate the severely degraded nature of a historical palimpsest, the overtext remains structurally intact, whereas

Fig. 5. Masked pretraining on the undertext head.

the undertext undergoes a multi-stage degradation process. It is first processed through the BSRGAN [22] degradation pipeline to introduce complex and non-uniform degradation. Subsequently, it is subjected to a randomized flaking mask that drops out between 30% and 50% of its remaining ink pixels. Finally, these text layers are composited onto complex backgrounds, sampled either from text-free manuscript patches or synthetic noise, using luminance-based subtractive alpha-blending to mimic how historical inks absorb into uneven parchment.

Fig. 6. Synthetic training samples.

4.2 Training Details

The network was implemented in PyTorch [23] and trained utilizing a single NVIDIA A100 GPU. The network weights were initialized using Xavier initialization [24] with a scaling gain of 0.02, and Instance Normalization [25] was applied across both the generator and discriminator networks to mitigate batch dependency. During training, input images were resized to 286×286 pixels and randomly cropped to 256×256 pixels to provide spatial data augmentation, utilizing a batch size of 4. The model was optimized using the Adam optimizer [26] with an initial learning rate of 1×10^{-4} and momentum parameters $\beta_1 = 0.5$

and $\beta_2 = 0.999$. To stabilize the adversarial training process, a Least Squares GAN (LSGAN) [27] formulation was utilized. The training was executed over a total of 50 epochs, systematically split into 10 epochs of pretraining followed by 40 epochs of full end-to-end training.

5 Evaluation

Since the ground truth does not exist for real palimpsests, the evaluation is divided into two phases. A quantitative analysis was done using synthetic data, followed by a qualitative visual assessment on patches from Codex XL. The results were compared to the performance of the standard BDeN model.

5.1 Quantitative Evaluation on Synthetic Data

Quantitative evaluation was performed on a test set of 1,000 synthetic palimpsest images with known ground truths. Image reconstruction quality was assessed using Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR), Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) [30], and Learned Perceptual Image Patch Similarity (LPIPS) [31]. Furthermore, because the ultimate goal of palimpsest restoration is transcription, Character Error Rate (CER) was calculated using the TrOCR [29] model to explicitly quantify the legibility of the recovered undertext and overtext. Table 1 summarizes the results. Examples of the reconstructed outputs of the synthetic samples are shown in Fig. 7 (for undertext), and in Fig. 8 (for overtext).

Fig. 7. Reconstructed undertext from synthetic inputs.

Fig. 8. Reconstructed overtext from synthetic inputs.

Table 1. Quantitative comparison of reconstruction performance on overtext and undertext.

Overtext				
Method	PSNR (dB) \uparrow	SSIM \uparrow	LPIPS \downarrow	CER (%) \downarrow
Standard BID	19.622	0.861	0.157	11.30
Ours	22.441	0.927	0.061	9.12
Undertext				
Standard BID	8.714	0.652	0.572	100.00
Ours	21.221	0.924	0.114	21.07

Fig. 9. Reconstructed undertext from patches of Codex XL. The image is oriented according to the undertext for better visibility.

5.2 Qualitative Comparison on Codex XL

To validate the model’s practical effectiveness, a qualitative comparison was performed on a selected set of patches from Codex XL. The outputs are presented in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10. The visual assessment is done against the outputs from the standard BID model.

5.3 Ablation Study

To validate the specific architectural and methodological contributions of our proposed framework, we conducted a systematic ablation study. We isolated the key components designed to handle the severe degradation of the undertext and evaluated their individual impact on both quantitative metrics (using our synthetic test set) and qualitative legibility (on real manuscript patches). Table 2 summarizes the results. The qualitative assessment is presented in Fig. 11.

Table 2. Ablation study on undertext reconstruction.

Model	Excluded Component	PSNR \uparrow	SSIM \uparrow	LPIPS \downarrow	CER (%) \downarrow
Baseline	All proposed modules	8.714	0.652	0.572	100.00
Model A	Masked pretraining	17.708	0.891	0.200	29.59
Model B	CBAM & dilated ResBlocks	9.394	0.732	0.512	91.05
Model C	\mathcal{L}_{feat} & \mathcal{L}_{conn}	18.856	0.906	0.132	22.53
Ours	None (full method)	21.221	0.924	0.114	21.07

Fig. 10. Reconstructed overtext from patches of Codex XL.

Fig. 11. Effect of each proposed component on reconstruction of undertext from a real palimpsest patch.

5.4 Discussion and Limitations

Quantitative and qualitative evaluations demonstrate that the proposed method outperforms the standard BID baseline, with particularly substantial gains in undertext reconstruction (Table 1 and Fig. 9). However, visual inspections reveal that our method occasionally underperforms the baseline in reconstructing the overtext (Fig. 10). This trade-off is primarily caused by the Feature Consistency Loss (\mathcal{L}_{feat}), which explicitly forces the shared encoder to prioritize undertext features, slightly diminishing its capacity to represent the top text layer. Furthermore, the ablation study confirms the individual effectiveness of the proposed components (Table 2). The inclusion of CBAM attention modules and Dilated Residual Blocks yielded the most significant performance contribution. Masked pretraining also provided substantial gains in overall stroke continuity. Finally, while the specialized objective functions (\mathcal{L}_{feat} and \mathcal{L}_{conn}) exhibited a smaller quantitative effect, they still provide regularizations that improved the functional legibility of the undertext (Fig. 11).

6 Conclusion and Future Work

In this paper, we presented an enhanced Blind Image Decomposition (BID) network specifically tailored for the complex task of palimpsest restoration. Unlike many traditional computational approaches that rely on Multispectral Imaging (MSI) data, our proposed method separates overlapping text layers using only standard RGB images. To address the severe degradation of undertext, we introduced a context-aware decoder integrated with Convolutional Block Attention Modules (CBAM) and Dilated Residual Blocks, effectively expanding the network’s spatial receptive field to bridge massive structural gaps. Furthermore, a masked pretraining phase and specialized loss functions, Connectivity Loss (\mathcal{L}_{conn}) and Feature Consistency Loss (\mathcal{L}_{feat}), were implemented to explicitly enforce continuous character trajectories. Quantitative evaluation on a synthetic dataset (Table. 1), combined with qualitative assessments on manuscript patches from the Codex XL palimpsest (Fig. 9), demonstrated that our proposed method outperforms the standard BID baseline. The most notable achievement was the improvement in the legibility of the degraded undertext. The visual assessments highlighted a trade-off where overtext reconstruction slightly diminished in favor of isolating the undertext (Fig. 10), primarily due to the prioritization enforced by \mathcal{L}_{feat} . Given that the main focus was given to recovering the faded undertext, this can be seen as an acceptable compromise.

Deep learning tools like this represent a step forward for cultural heritage preservation. By enhancing the readability of degraded artifacts to the point where automatic transcription becomes viable, this methodology breaks down traditional barriers. It ensures that historians, researchers, and members of the general public without specialized paleographic background knowledge can easily access and study lost historical materials. Future work will focus on refining feature disentanglement to balance the reconstruction quality of both text layers equally.

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